

Area 1: Recycled fibres

1. To which point are you involved in the value chain of recycled fibres?
2. Which products exist in your market segment, that contain a certain percentage of recycled fibres?
3. What forms of recycling of cotton, PET, PA, EL and viscose (cellulose regenerate) fibres are used in your region/business/products?
4. What are common problems of recycling the 5 above mentioned materials (including blends) in your region/business/products?

Area 2: Technical requirements (mechanical, optical, haptic)

1. Which are the technical criteria (parameters) of used fibres that are important for your products or your field of research?
2. Could you specify the latitude or range those parameters need to attain to be used in the production process?
3. Which experiences do you have in terms of purchasing recycled fibres (domestic, abroad)?

Area 3: Facilitate market uptake

1. What's the cost gap between recycled and primary fibre of the 5 mentioned materials in your region/business/product?
2. If you already use recycled fibres: what is the cost gap of recycled fibres from the sources you know (e.g. domestic, import from low wage countries)?
3. What are the economic boundaries, that hinder the market uptake of recycled fibres?
4. What are consumers ready to pay and at which level is the loss of margin, or which loss would be acceptable in your company's / brand's opinion, respectively?

Is there anything else what is important to you? Feel free to describe your topic in addition!